

Hatti Heritage: Unveiling the Traditions and Tales of Trans-Giri

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Abstract:

Tribe is a distinct group of people with common lineage and culture, is recognized as Scheduled Tribes in India. One such community is from Himachal Pradesh, which recently received tribal status in the Trans-Giri region of Himachal Pradesh, known as Hatti. The Hatti community is associated with the Trans-Giri region, situated in the *Sirmaur* district of Himachal Pradesh. The term "Hatti" is derived from the word "*haat*," meaning buying and selling everyday items in the market. This research paper explores the customs, traditions, and legal system of the Hatti community using qualitative research methodology. Data was collected through interviews, newspapers, books, and focus-group discussions among Hatti community members. Paper includes the popular folk tale of *Dula*, which tells the story of his wife *Sarahliti*. The caste structure, marriage, primary deities, worship practises, etc. are expounded upon in the next section. This article also includes the traditional village council system known as "*Khumblee*."

Keywords: Trans-Giri, Tribe, Hatti, Khumabli, Thagde

Introduction:

The Hatti community or tribe constitutes a distinct group of people who share common lineage and culture. Numerous such tribes exist in practically every state in India; as per Article 342 of the Indian Constitution, there are more than 700 tribal groups. These tribes have been officially recognized as Scheduled Tribes. As per the 2011 census, these Scheduled Tribes comprise approximately 8.6% of India's total population, amounting to around 10.4 crore individuals. Currently, this figure has increased, as many communities have been accorded the status of tribes since 2011. One such community is from Himachal Pradesh, which recently received tribal status. This community resides in the Trans-Giri region of Himachal Pradesh, known as Hatti. However, the demand for tribal recognition by this community is not new; it dates back nearly 55 years. It is noteworthy that along with Sirmaur, the area of Jaunsar Babar, which is part of Uttarakhand (established as the 27th state of India on November 9, 2000), shares similar folk culture, traditions, lifestyle, and language as the Trans-Giri region of Sirmaur. Despite this, Jaunsar was designated as a tribal area in 1967, while the Trans-Giri region remained deprived of this benefit. Nevertheless, the local people of this region have been persistently struggling to have their area declared a tribal region since 1967.

In 1967, a few personalities from Sirmaur, including Prof. Amar Singh (Mila Village), Dr. Roop Kumar (Bhaluna Village), Prof. Jogiram (Kamaru Village), Prof. Sundar Singh (Kandundugan Village), among others, initiated efforts to obtain tribal status for the people of the Trans-Giri region. They visited Dehradun to discuss and deliberate with the people of Jaunsar Babar and prepared an extensive report, which was forwarded to the Ministry of Tribal Affairs. During this period, Thakur Sain Negi from Himachal Pradesh was also actively involved in this matter and made significant contributions. As a result, in 2023, the longstanding struggle of the people bore fruit. Now, 154 panchayats from four assembly constituencies will benefit from this decision. These panchayats include not only individuals from the Hatti community but also representatives from 14 castes and sub-castes within this community. This includes various tribes and sub-tribes, from *Khash* and *Kanait* to Scheduled Castes and Tribes.

Objectives of the Research Paper:

1. To provide insight into the socio-economic background of the Hatti community.
2. To describe the customs and traditions of the Hatti community.
3. To elucidate the legal system of the Hatti community.

Research Methodology:

Qualitative research methodology has been employed in this research paper. It is a descriptive study that utilizes various primary sources such as interviews and newspapers articles. Also, various secondary sources books and research papers have also been utilized. Data was collected through in-depth interviews of prominent personalities and focus-group discussions were also conducted among female and male members of Hatti community.

Geographical Overview of the Trans-Giri Region:

The Giri and Tons river basins, which are both Yamuna tributaries, form the border between Himachal Pradesh and Uttarakhand, where the Hatti homeland is situated. The border between the two states is denoted by the Tons. Before Jaunsar Bawar's secession in 1814, the Hattis who now reside in the trans-Giri region of Himachal Pradesh and Jaunsar Bawar in Uttarakhand were a part of the Sirmaur royal estate.

The Hatti community is associated with the Trans-Giri region, situated in the Sirmaur district of Himachal Pradesh, predominantly nestled within the outer Himalayas of the Shivalik Range, lying between 77° 01' 12" to 77° 49' 40" east longitude and 33° 22' 30" to 34° 01' 20" north latitude. This region comprises lofty peaks such as *Churdhar* and *Churdhar Chandni*, the latter standing at an elevation of 11,982 feet. Other prominent peaks include *Dhar Taproli*, *Dhar Nohra*, *Haripur* (standing at 8809 feet), *Dudham Dhar*, and *Shilai Dhar*, which converge to form the *Naira* River valley, eventually merging into the *Tons* River.

The *Giri* river demarcates the areas inhabited by the Hatti community from the rest of the regions in Sirmaur state. It is owing to this river that this area is known as Trans-Giri or *Giripar*. This river originates from the Kupar hills of Kotkhai Jubbal in Shimla district and flows in a southeast direction. To its east lies the Tons River, which separates Sirmaur from Uttarakhand. The area east of the Tons River is Jaunsar Babar, which was part of the Sirmaur state before 1815. Post the Gurkha War, the British annexed it and merged it into Dehradun.

Naming of the Hatti Community:

The term "Hatti" is derived from the word "*haat*," which literally means buying and selling everyday items in the market. Local people explain that in the remote areas of Sirmaur district, there were no markets available for the residents. Therefore, these people used to form groups and visit nearby markets to purchase essential items and sell their homegrown products. In the mountain dialect, "*haat*" is also referred to as "*nagarati*." People would travel from their homes to the market once or twice a year, they carried goods on their backs such as grain, pulses, vegetables, wool, and other commodities. Along with these items, they also carried some money. They would then return home with items like jaggery, sugar, salt, cloth, etc., in exchange for their goods and money. It is noteworthy that when they went to the market, they also carried food items, bedding, etc., and would camp in the forests, spending several days there before returning home. As mentioned earlier, people (residents of villages and surrounding areas) used to go to the market in groups because they feared violent animals and robbers along the way. In the past, markets used to be held in places like Lahore, Allahabad, Delhi, Patna, Ambala, etc., as described in mountain songs.

Folk Tale of Dula:

Dula was a prominent figure in the Pundari region, known as the head of the Pundar area. His wife from Sarahan (*Saraon ki dhayain*) was very attentive to the simple things, meaning she was modest. Dula married this modest girl from Pundari. She was very beautiful to look at. One day, after marriage, she expressed her desire to her husband that if he loved her, he should get her gold jewellery made from Lahore because Lahore gold was of very good quality. It is said that even today, this gold is found in the areas of Jubbal, Balsan, and Chaupal in Shimla, which is generally of a reddish colour. In order to fulfill his wife's wish, Dula Pundari set out to buy gold from Lahore. During this journey, he was accompanied by 18 young men. After buying the gold, when he returned to Pundar, Dula had gold jewellery made for his wife, Sarahliti. A mountain song (Haarul) has also been composed on this incident, the lyrics of which go something like this: '*Rani lagi Sarahliti sunagunari bai, mukhe layo dulea sunagan garaye*'. Meaning, Dula's queen (wife) Sarahliti, while getting gold jewellery made for herself, asked her husband to bring her jewellery of better quality.

Castes and Sub-castes:

These two Hatti clans—Trans-Giri and Jaunsar Bawar—share customs and frequently get married to each other. Nonetheless, there is a very strict caste structure in the community; intercaste marriages are customarily forbidden. The *Bhat* and *Khash* are upper castes, and the *Badhois* are lower castes.

There is no dominance of any single caste in the Trans-Giri region; rather, many castes and sub-castes reside in this area. The major ones include: Rajput, Brahmin, Bhatt, Kanait, Khosh Kanait, Deva, Kaoli, Chammar, Dhaaki Baadi, Lauhar, Natuwa, Turi, Tarkhan, Mauchi, etc. Each of these castes has its own distinct occupations.

The traditional elites continue to hold a strong hold on both the social and political realms of rural Sirmauri society. The majority of *Lambardars*, *Zaildars*, and *Pujaris* sit in formal establishment chairs and concurrently oversee formal and informal organisations. The decision-making process is dominated by Rajputs and Brahmins because of their perceived caste supremacy, casting doubt on these Khumblis' neutrality. However, the Scheduled Castes are not allowed to participate in any way in the Khumbli. They live in a situation of supremacy since the village Devta controls all aspect of their socio-economic existence. The Devta institution's regulations are designed to inflict "*Dev Dosh*," or divine wrath, upon anyone who breaks them. The Devta institution also determines how various castes relate to one another and gives them tasks with promises made to one another, a practise known as "*Akhar Paur*." Due to women's exclusion from the divine institution and social hierarchy resulting from ritual impurity and Scheduled Castes' exclusion, the Khumbli's functions are anti-equal and undemocratic. Three factors of dominance—ritual status, land ownership, and numerical strength—allow the upper castes to control the power system. They live on generally fertile land holdings, while the lower castes own relatively little land, which is typically unfertile.

Marriage System:

In the Hatti community, the practice of polyandry was prevalent, meaning one wife, many husbands. Under this practice, a girl's marriage was typically arranged with the eldest son of the family, but she was considered the wife of all the brothers of that family. This practice is also observed in some areas of Shimla district along with Sirmaur. Additionally, this practice

was very prevalent in Kinnaur. However, with time, very few examples of this practice are seen now, mainly due to the refusal of the younger generation to accept it. Nonetheless, there are still many people and families who are bound by this practice, citing reasons similar to those in other places, such as maintaining family unity, avoiding division of lands, and staying away from conflicts.

The Hatti community does not practice dowry. Previously, during the marriage of a girl, two or three people from each household of the entire village used to go to the girl's house. This practice still continues. However, many people have now started the tradition of taking a wedding procession.

Major Deities:

The Hatti community also worships various deities. Every village has its own deities. Mainly, the people of Jonsar Bawar, Ladhi, Shilai, Renuka, Rajgarh, Solan, and the Theog region of Shimla district, and the people of the Jubbal-Kotkhai region consider *Shri Gul Devta Churdhar* as their family deity. Even in many regions of Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh, people consider *Mahasu Devta* as their family deity. *Shri Gul* and *Chandreshwar* were two brothers. *Shri Gul Maharaj* is considered the family deity in almost all regions, but there are also temples of *Chandreshwar Maharaj* in many regions.

Mahasu Deity:

Image 1- “*Mahasu Devta*” Temple in Hanol

Image 2- One of the “*Mahasu Devta*” Palanquin

Mahasu deity is composed of four brothers: *Boodha*, *Chaalda Maharaj*, *Vaashik*, and *Pavaasi*. *Chaalda Maharaj* is always in motion. The shrine of *Boodha Mahasu* is located in Hanol (Uttarakhand). *Vaashik* Maharaj resides in *Vaashik*, while *Pavaasi* Maharaj resides in Thandyaar. Each of the four brothers has their own temple dedicated to *Mahasu* deity in different villages. Additionally, deities like *Maheshwar*, *Shri Gul*, *Peer*, *Vanaad*, *Kailu*, *Daum*, *Parsuram*, and *Vijat* Maharaj are worshipped in various villages. Every village also has its own goddesses, worshipped by the Hatti community, including Kali, Thaari, Shoolini, Kali Chamunda, Nagar Koti, Bhimakali, Haateshwari, Surkhandaa, Valla Sundari, Katakana Mata, Jwala Mata, Santoshi Mata, Bagula Mukhi, and countless others.

Worship Rituals:

During the dawn also known as *Brahma Muhurta*, between 3 to 5 in the morning, the names of deities are chanted by the *Dhakis*, *Vaadis*, and *Lohars* to awaken the deities so that people can worship them. The worship of deities is conducted by Brahmins in the morning and

evening. The village people contribute offerings to the priest Brahmins. Each village provides Brahmins with offerings twice a year according to the yield of crops.

On every Sakranti (day of the solar month), clarified butter (ghee) and money are offered at the temple, where a portion of the money is given to the Brahmin and the rest is deposited in the village treasury. Similar offerings are also made to the *Bajantari* (the one who plays musical instruments during worship). Village deities are highly revered as protectors against major calamities. The Hatti community holds deep faith in their deities.

Special Festivals and Cuisine

The Hatti community celebrates several special festivals, including:

- *Budhi Diwali*: It is observed a month after Diwali since it is thought that word of Lord Ram's arrival in Ayodhya reached late in this area.
- *Vishu* also known as *Vaisakhi*, marked by fairs in the Hatti region.
- "*Haryali*" which is celebrated during the month of *Sawan*, featuring wrestling matches.
- "*Shanyali*", also observed during *Sawan*, featuring a special type of bread offered first to water deities and then distributed among families.
- *Guggal* is a festival associated with *Peer Baba*, involving worship of the serpent deity and *Guggal* Maharaj, where people offer wheat flour dough to *Guggal* Maharaj, who travels throughout the region in a palanquin eight days before the festival.
- "*Shant*" that is celebrated in *Shri Gul*, depicting the peacefulness of Lord *Shiva* and Goddess *Kali*, featuring a limber showing the battle between the Kauravas and Pandavas, accompanied by folk dances and offerings of goat, pumpkin, and coconut to Goddess *Kali*, while *Shri Gul* deity receives sattvic meals.
- *Maghi* Festival is the one where goats are slaughtered on the 28th day of *Poush* (December-January) month and consumed throughout the month due to the severe cold in the region, leading to a higher consumption of meat.
- *Maun* is a festival observed during the month of *Aashaad* (June-July) by Rajputs to demonstrate their valour, involving the grinding of *Timbar* (stem of herbal plant), followed by their immersion in the river, with attempts by Rajputs from other areas to stop the immersion, resulting in a game where the leaves, when mixed in the river

water and intoxicate the fish, which are then collected by locals for distribution to their respective homes, accompanied by singing and dancing.

During these festivals, various types of delicacies are prepared, such as *Sidku* or *Siddu* (a steamed dish made from a yeast-based dough filled with sweet and savory and eaten with ghee), *Khinda* (a halwa made by boiling flour and jaggery in water), *Ulule* (a snack made from rice flour), *Ade* (a dish made from barley), *Dhidki* (a dish made from buckwheat flour), *Patande* (made of wheat flour), *Kukwa* (a local green leafy vegetable), *Dhindare* (a dish made from arbi leaves and vegetables), *Khardo* (a special dish made from millet, rice, and buckwheat), *Gulti* (meat of goat), *Khuble* (a dish made from jaggery, flour, and goat fat), *Mashal Bhat* (rice made from local lentils and rice) etc.

Image 3- Siddu with ghee and chutney

Image 4- Khinda with ghee

Khumblee/Khumlee as a System of Justice:

The Hatti community is governed by a traditional council known as *Khumblee* or *Khumlee*, which functions similarly to the *Khap* Panchayats of the Haryana state, overseeing communal matters. This tradition of *Khumblee* has persisted since the reign of kings. In the justice system of *Khumblee*, the main *panch* (panchayat members) preside, elected by the villagers. These *panch* members are referred to as "*thagade*" in the local dialect. These "*thagade*" individuals engage in discussions regarding various issues pertinent to the Hatti community.

These "*thagade*" members are respected figures within their clans and families. The complainant presents evidence in favor of their side before these "*thagade*" members, whose deliberation and judgment hold significant weight in the *Khumblee*. Furthermore, the experiences of the village elders are also utilized in the adjudication of each case. Local

inhabitants recall a time when people neither had access to courts nor any recognition. Consequently, all decisions were made within the *Khumblee*, a tradition that persists to this day.

Regardless of social status—be it rich or poor, influential or ordinary—decisions pertaining to all individuals were made within this *Khumblee*. It is noteworthy that if any individual failed to abide by the decisions of the village *panch*, they were subjected to social ostracization, locally termed as "*vanja*." This ostracization meant that no member of the village would engage with them or participate in any significant events such as births, deaths, marriages, or any other auspicious or inauspicious occasions at their house.

Thus, adherence to the decisions of the *Khumblee* was imperative, and any dissenting individual would face consequences. The village *panch* would impose fines of 100 rupees and sacrifice a goat, or alternatively, the guilty party would be subjected to a goat sacrifice as a form of punishment. The meat from this sacrifice would be used to provide a meal for the entire village, after which the guilty individual would be reintegrated into the community.

Image 5: Khumblee Meeting

Formation of Khumblee Council:

The *Khumblee* council is neither elected through any formal elections nor is it ever dissolved. It prioritizes individuals who seek the welfare of the village. The "*numberdar*" holds a special position in the village and is responsible for convening the *Khumblee* when necessary. Whenever villagers conduct *Khumblee* outside the village, they give a nominal fee of 2 rupees to the responsible "*numberdar*" as a token and request him to inform the villagers about the upcoming *Khumblee* so that everyone can attend. Subsequently, the prominent

individuals of the village gather and impartial decisions are made during the panchayat meeting.

Many times, decisions made in courts are referred back to the *Khumblee* for consideration. Even today, this council system remains prevalent in the Hatti society. Decisions made within the council are considered valid and often come at a much lower cost compared to the expenses incurred in courts. When a decision is made both parties are fined 100 rupees each. This fine is crucial as a decision without it is not considered legitimate. Later, the collected fines are either offered to the deity in the temple or distributed among the *panch* members.

Even today, people have immense faith in the Khumblee/Khumlee system. Women also play a significant role in the Khumblee/Khumlee, especially in matters concerning them. It is stated that the Hatti community views the Khumblee/Khumlee not as a political institution but as a safeguard for their culture. This institution ensures accessible and affordable justice, which is why the Hatti people uphold it.

Conclusion:

The Hatti community is still recognized for its unique customs and traditions. The Hatti Community is a close-knit group in Himachal Pradesh, particularly concentrated in the Shillai area of the Sirmaur district. Let's recollect some interesting facts about this community mentioned earlier. The Hattis acquire their name from their custom of working in small-town "haats," where they sell locally grown produce, livestock, wool, and crops. Hatti men frequently don a characteristic white headdress during ceremonial events. Their territory lies in the basin of the Giri and Tons rivers, which are both tributaries of the Yamuna, and crosses the border between Himachal Pradesh and Uttarakhand. Before Jaunsar Bawar's secession in 1814, the Hattis residing in the trans-Giri area of Himachal Pradesh and Jaunsar Bawar, Uttarakhand, were a part of the royal estate of Sirmaur. One Hatti clan resides in Trans-Giri, while the other is in Jaunsar Bawar. Within the society, a rather severe caste structure is in place despite shared traditions.

Hatti community is famous for its Community Governance. Similar to the "*khaps*" of Haryana, the Hattis are ruled by a traditional council known as "*khumbli*." Community issues are decided by this council. It's interesting to note that even with the implementation of the

Panchayati raj system, the Khumbli's authority is still unquestioned. In the regions of Sirmour and Shimla, the Hattis hold a considerable influence in approximately nine Assembly seats.

Since 1967, the Hattis have been requesting designation as a Scheduled Tribe (ST). Like the residents of Jaunsar Bawar, Uttarakhand, they also demand recognition. In 2023 they have been added to the Scheduled tribe list.

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